

Skills 4 eosc

D7.3 - Report on CCs and user support networks and recommendations for networks evolution

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Deliverable Abstract

This deliverable documents the Skills4EOSC Competence Centres and User Support Networks while providing guidance for their sustainability. It serves a dual purpose: reporting on the current project-based structures and outlining strategies for their continuation after project funding ends. The focus is on the governance, operational frameworks, and collaboration mechanisms that allow these networks to continue operating after the Skills4EOSC project concludes.

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TERMINOLOGY

<https://eosc-portal.eu/glossary>

Terminology/Acronym	Definition
BMC	Business Model Canvas
CC	Competence Centre
CCs	Competence Centres
CCNet	Competence Centre Network
ELSI	Ethical Legal Societal Implications
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
FbD	FAIR-by-Design
GA	General Assembly
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
LoI	Letter of Intent
MoU	Memorandum of Understanding
MVS	Minimum Viable Skillsets
OS	Open Science
RDM	Research Data Management

USC	User Support Channel
USCs	User Support Channels
USN	User Support Network

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Executive summary

This report provides a comprehensive analysis of Competence Centres (CCs) and User Support Networks (USNs) established under the Skills4EOSC project, presenting recommendations for their sustainable evolution. Skills4EOSC has successfully created a coordinated Network of Competence Centres across Europe to support Open Science practices by providing expertise in FAIR data principles and digital research management.

The document outlines the governance structure, collaboration framework, and coordination mechanisms of the Competence Centre Network (CCNet), which currently includes nine operational Competence Centres located in Italy, Greece, Finland, Sweden, North Macedonia, France, Luxembourg, Poland, and Germany. The Network has been designed with sustainability in mind, featuring a robust governance model with a General Assembly and Presidency, supported by clear membership terms and engagement processes.

Parallel to the CCNet, the report details the User Support Network (USN) initiative, which brings together User Support Channels (USCs) from various institutions to facilitate knowledge exchange and promote Open Science practices through direct technical and operational support. This network serves as a complementary structure to the Competence Centres, focusing on practical assistance to researchers.

The technical infrastructure supporting both networks is examined, including essential tools and services, alongside recommendations for their continued development. A sustainability strategy outlines paths for continued community engagement beyond the project's lifetime, focusing on the Competence Centre Network as a lightweight organizational structure to maintain and evolve project outcomes.

The report concludes with strategic recommendations for existing and new Competence Centres, User Support Channels, and their respective networks, emphasizing the importance of standardized knowledge management, enhanced cross-channel collaboration, and clear alignment with the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) ecosystem. These recommendations

provide a roadmap for continued evolution, ensuring that the infrastructure established during the Skills4EOSC project can thrive independently and continue to advance Open Science principles across Europe.

1 Introduction

1.1 Scope and objectives

This deliverable addresses the development and evolution of Competence Centres (CCs) and User Support Networks (USNs) within the Skills4EOSC project framework, providing a comprehensive overview of their current status and recommendations for future sustainability. The primary objective is to document the established structure of the Competence Centre Network, detailing its governance model, membership framework, and operational mechanisms that enable knowledge sharing and capacity building in Open Science across Europe.

The report has dual scope, serving both as documentation of the current project-based structures and as a forward-looking guide for sustaining these networks beyond the Skills4EOSC project timeline. It provides a detailed examination of how the Competence Centres Network has been designed to operate independently after project funding ends, with particular attention to governance processes, collaboration frameworks, and sustainability strategies.

For the User Support Network, the deliverable documents the initiative's current implementation, services, and activities while proposing pathways for its continued operation through inter-institutional cooperation. The report aims to guide both existing and potential new members of these networks by clarifying roles, responsibilities, and benefits of participation, thereby ensuring continued advancement of Open Science practices across European research communities.

1.2 Document structure

The document is structured into seven main sections, each addressing key aspects of the Competence Centres Network and User Support Network:

- Section 1 describes the scope, objective and structure of this deliverable.
- Section 2 introduces the Skills4EOSC Competence Centres Network, describing its mission, objectives, and the defined Charter that governs

membership. It provides an overview of the nine currently active Competence Centres, highlighting their individual specializations and contributions to the Network.

- Section 3 details the Network Coordination Structure, outlining the governance model, collaboration framework, and coordination mechanisms. This section also explains the alignment strategies for key outputs and provides practical guidance on how new Competence Centres can join the Network.
- Section 4 focuses on Technical Infrastructure and Services, describing the tools and technologies that support the Network's operations, including a strategy for service evolution.
- Section 5 examines the User Support Network initiative, defining its purpose, describing participating User Support Channels, and documenting the services, activities, and materials developed to facilitate knowledge exchange between user support teams.
- Section 6 addresses the Sustainability Approach for both short-term community-driven evolution (1-2 years post-project) requiring dedicated community resources, and long-term sustainability which may require additional national, regional, and pan-European funding.
- Section 7 provides specific Recommendations for existing and new Competence Centres, User Support Channels, and their respective networks, offering guidance for continued development and enhanced impact.

The document concludes with annexes containing draft versions of both the Memorandum of Understanding and the Letter of Intent, promissory documents outlining the commitment of the onboarding Competence Centres to the main objectives of the Competence Centres Network.

2 Skills4EOSC Competence Centres Network

Skills4EOSC aims at building a Coordinated Network of Competence Centres (CCNet) across Europe to support Open Science practices. These Competence Centres (CCs) serve as reference points in specific countries, regions, or domains for finding expertise in Open Science, FAIR data principles, and digital research management.

The CC Network is seen as the ultimate vehicle to attain the sustainability of the Skills4EOSC project results by the project participants. As one of the results of the project, CC Network has to be prepared to sustain itself and provide a pathway to continue the evolution of project outcomes. Therefore the charter of the Competence Centre network is aimed at the future after the formal end of the Skills4EOSC project.

The mission, goals and structure of the Competence Centres are defined in the Competence Centre Charter [\[R1\]](#). In section 2.1 and 2.2 we will provide a description of the CC Network and a short summary of the Charter that defines the Skills4EOSC CCs.

2.1 The CCs Network

Skills4EOSC Competence Centre Network is a lightweight organisation based on the in-kind contributions from its members providing the sustainable framework for the evolution of the outcomes of the Skills4EOSC project inline with the values and the definition of a Competence Centre.

The Competence Centres Network of Skills4EOSC has been initially established through the involvement of consortium partners, leveraging existing Competence Centres (such as ICDI) or those directly connected to project partners (such as the Open Science Cloud Competence Center in Greece). Subsequently, the Network has open up to the participation of external CCs and Contributors.

By joining the CC Network, Competence Centres agree to commit to further evolve the outcomes of the Skills4EOSC project to maximise their value for the network members.

Membership terms, admission criteria, rights and obligations of CCs and the organization and coordination of the Network are described in section 3.

2.1.1 Mission and objectives of the Network

The Network's mission encompasses facilitating information and experience exchange among members while sharing Open Science best practices. It focuses on advancing FAIR research through training and education initiatives, and disseminating Skills4EOSC outcomes. The Network provides support and guidance to research organizations and universities lacking a national coordination infrastructure on Open Science, while building strategic relationships with European and global entities interested in Open Science and EOSC.

The Network aims to create a framework that enables networking, peer-learning, and knowledge exchange between Competence Centres dedicated to Open Science. It is committed to promoting good practices and building capacity through educational programs, advisory services, events, and training opportunities. Additionally, the Network works to advance research integrity through strategic partnerships and advocacy efforts.

2.2 The CCs Charter

The Competence Centre Charter defines the shared mission, scope, and core features that characterise a Competence Centre (CC) within the Skills4EOSC Network.

It outlines the target stakeholders, the key characteristics and minimum requirements, as well as the portfolio of activities and services that a CC should demonstrate to be eligible for joining the Network.

The Charter serves as a reference framework to ensure coherence, quality, and impact across the pan-European network of CCs, supporting capacity building in Open Science, FAIR data, and the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC).

In the following sections, the main aspects of the Charter are presented.

2.2.1 Definition and Purpose

Skills4EOSC Competence Centres are dedicated to knowledge organization and transfer in Open Science and FAIR research management. They address skills shortages by offering training, connecting stakeholders to national and international programs, and serving as access points for networking. CCs must be recognized by the research community at national, regional, or thematic levels.

2.2.2 Mission

Their mission is to provide a shared hub of expertise for implementing Open Science and FAIR data principles, offering leadership, training, coordination, and cataloguing services. They pool expertise from research institutions, universities, and research infrastructures to support stakeholders in adopting OS policies and practices.

2.2.3 Target Audience

CCs serve diverse stakeholders including researchers and data stewards, decision makers and policymakers, government organizations and ministries, university networks and funding organizations, legal and ethical advisors, Research Performing Organizations, discipline-specific research communities, publishers, and citizen scientists.

2.2.4 Eligibility Requirements

To join the Skills4EOSC CCNet, a Competence Centre must demonstrate commitment to Open Science and FAIR principles, commit to adopting Skills4EOSC project outcomes, possess domain authority and expertise, maintain a network of Master Trainers with diverse skills, actively engage with target groups, provide training and support services, and effectively communicate and disseminate knowledge.

2.2.5 Activities and Services

CCs should offer an indicative set of activities including training courses using Skills4EOSC materials, community-specific training events, collection of user

feedback and needs assessment, adoption of Skills4EOSC methodology and quality assurance processes, maintenance of web presence and network interaction, and optional IT services based on community needs.

2.2.6 Support from Skills4EOSC

Skills4EOSC provides each CC with Training the Trainers programs designed on Minimum Viable Skillsets (MVS) for different professional profiles, along with methodologies for FAIR-by-design learning resources and quality assurance frameworks as well as MVS for further use.

2.3 CCs Registry Overview

CCs within the Skills4EOSC network are accessible in a Registry [R2] presented in a section of the project website. Currently, nine CCs are part of the Skills4EOSC Network, located in Italy, Greece, Finland, Sweden, North Macedonia, France, Luxembourg, Poland and Germany. However, talks are ongoing with other several institutions interested in becoming part of the Network in different European countries: Netherlands, Spain, Czech Republic, Turkey. In this section we will briefly summarise the main information about CCs that are currently part of the Network.

2.3.1 Italian Computing and Data Infrastructure (ICDI)

Establishment year

2018

History

The ICDI Competence Centre (ICDI-CC) [R3] was formed as a collaboration agreement between major Italian research organizations, with the aim of coordinating their participation in EOSC projects. ICDI was one of the four founding members of the EOSC Association when it was established as a legal entity. Currently, 24 Italian organizations are part of the EOSC Association, with most being members of ICDI.

Skills4EOSC CC Entry since

2023

Competences

- Policy and strategic guidance
- Legal and ethical
- Research data management, FAIR principles, data management plan
- Open Access
- Domain and sector specific

Services offered

- Training courses
- Periodic community engagement events (OpenScienceCafé)
- Guides, guidelines and good practices
- Support and advice
- Catalogue management and editing

2.3.2 Open Science Cloud Competence Center in Greece

Establishment year

1998

History

GRNET [R4] has coordinated Greek national IT initiatives for research and technology over the past 30 years, bringing together experts in research networking, cloud computing, and data services. As coordinator of HellasGrid (2003-2010) and the national HPC Competence Center, GRNET serves as the central point for high-performance computing activities and resources across academia, government, and industry. GRNET is a key contributor to Greece's National Plan for Open Science and founding member of the Hellenic Open Science Initiative (HOSI), representing Greece in the European Open Science Cloud Association. GRNET coordinates all education and research e-infrastructures in Greece, providing technological support to academic institutions and public agencies. GRNET is currently establishing an Open Science Cloud Competence Center to build collaborative relationships within the Greek open science ecosystem, aligned with the Greek National Digital Skills Academy.

Skills4EOSC CC Entry since

2023

Competences

- Services for Open Science
- Consultancy - strategic guidance
- Policy and strategic guidance
- Legal and ethical
- Research data management, FAIR principles, data management plan
- Expertise in EOSC Architecture as defined in SRIA and EOSC related procedures and policies.
- Competencies that are not currently on board are complemented by the pool of experts within the HOSI members and other R&E institutions

Services offered

- Services for Open Science
- Service portfolio management
- Training
- Consultancy
- Service Onboarding Support

2.3.3 The CSC Research Data Management Competence Center (Finland)

Establishment year

2021

History

The CSC Research Data Management Competence Center [R5] has been established to support skills and competencies on Open Science and implementation of the FAIR principles for research data. The main target group is data management professionals in research organisations in Finland.

Skills4EOSC CC Entry since

2024

Competences

- Open Science and FAIR data management

- Best practices for managing, reusing, publishing and storing research data
- Knowledge of data management services and tools
- Training, consultation, knowledge building
- Coordination, networking, dissemination

Services offered

- Training
- Workshops
- Consultation
- Support
- Online courses
- Guidelines
- Training materials
- Network coordination
- Data support coffee
- Data chat
- Newsletters

2.3.4 Swedish National Data Service (SND)

Establishment year

2008

History

SND [R6] has far reaching foundations, stretching back before its current iteration which began in 2008. It began as a repository for Social Sciences data in 1981 under the name Swedish Social Science Data Service, before incorporating data from humanities and health sciences in 2008 – henceforth to be known as Swedish National Data Service. In 2016, environmental and climate data was incorporated to the repository, and from 2018, SND accepts data from all disciplines.

Skills4EOSC CC Entry since

2024

Competences

- Legal and ethical

- Research data management
- FAIR principles
- Data management plans
- Open Access
- Domain and sector specific
- PID policies
- Metadata standards
- IT and infrastructure
- Trusted Digital Repositories
- Training and outreach

Services offered

- National support on the road to open science
- National research data catalogue
- Development of tools and services
- Training and information
- Collaborations and networks

2.3.5 Open Science and Research Data Competence Centre OSC@MK (North Macedonia)

Establishment year

2024

History

The initial activities regarding open science and research data management in North Macedonia were done within the NI4OS-Europe project, with the establishment of NOSCI@MK. With all public universities coming together to acknowledge the importance of practicing open science led by the Ss. Cyril and Methodius University that also represents the country in the EOSC Association, the next step has been the development of Open Science infrastructure (the OSC lab) and the Open Science and Research Data Competence Centre [R7] that will continue to drive the implementation of the adopted Open Science Policy.

Skills4EOSC CC Entry since

2024

Competences

- Putting Open Science into practice
- Research Data management
- Implementation of the FAIR principles
- Open Science ELSI aspects

Services offered

- OS related training (formal and informal)
- Data management support and tools
- Policy development templates and guidance
- Open Science Lab

2.3.6 Recherche Data Gouv (France)

Establishment year

2022

History

The 2nd French National Plan for Open Science, published in 2021, present global actions on three main axes: open access, open data, and open source codes. One of the actions under the 2nd axis is to create a national federated platform to support the national community on the path to opening their data. Recherche Data Gouv [R8] started as a multi-years project in 2021, with the aim to build a sustainable ecosystem, which officially opened and launched in July 2022.

Skills4EOSC CC Entry since

2024

Competences

- Data management, especially sharing and publishing
- Open Science practices
- FAIR principles implementation
- OS ELSI aspects

- Disciplinary data support
- Research Output Management services (consulting on data repository and data curation)

Services offered

- Training
- Support and advice (All aspects of RDM)
- Ready-to-reuse learning materials
- National policy coordination
- Working Groups (brainstorming, networking)

2.3.7 Luxembourg National Data Service LNDS

Establishment year

2022

History

In respective strategies on the national data economy and national research and innovation, Luxembourg has identified data reuse as a key enabler of data-driven innovation. In line with the EU Data Strategy and in preparation for the upcoming Data Governance Act, in 2022, the Luxembourgish Government and has established the Luxembourg National Data Service [R9]. The LNDS provides services enabling responsible secondary use of public sector data for public and private partners and support the sharing and re-use of public sector data, in a trustable manner.

Skills4EOSC CC Entry since

2024

Competences

- FAIR data management and stewardship
- Training
- Community management
- Sharing sensitive controlled-access data
- Data preservation
- Ethical Legal Societal Implications (ELSI) in data sharing

Services offered

- Data Management and Stewardship Support
- Data Management National Community of Practice
- Research Data Archival
- Data Access Request and Review
- Data Cataloguing
- ELSI and Data Governance and Consulting

2.3.8 Open Science Competence Center OSCC (Poland)

Establishment year

2018

History

The Open Science Competence Center [R10] was established at Gdańsk University of Technology Library in 2018 as part of the Bridge of Data project. It serves as a support hub for scholarly communication, offering training, consultancy, and events that promote open science principles. OSCC assists researchers throughout the data lifecycle, ensuring compliance with FAIR and CARE principles by improving metadata, standardizing descriptions, and enhancing data reusability. The center maintains a certified research data repository, a Digital Pathology system for DIACOMS images, and an Open Access repository for publications and related digital resources.

Skills4EOSC CC Entry since

2025

Competences

- Overview of open research data (FAIR and CARE principles, research data lifecycle)
- Data Management Plans (national and EU grant applications)
- Thematic approaches to sharing data (scientific discipline approach)
- Metadata
- Legal support (data licensing, data protection, reusing data, ethic)
- Open Science policy and governance
- Scientific evaluation and recognition

- Open Scholarly Communication
- Open Access, Plan S (implications and requirements)
- Financing publishing in Open Access model (institutional and national initiatives and programmes)
- Open Educational Resources
- Using the Open Research Data Catalog – Bridge of Data Repository (depositing datasets)

Services offered

- OS related training, workshops and consultations
- Research Data Management support and advice
- Information and knowledge building
- Usage of services and tools

2.3.9 RDM@KIT

Establishment year

2016

History

The RDM@KIT [R11] was established in 2016 alliance between the Research Services Department of the KIT Library and the Scientific Computer Center (SCC) at KIT for supporting and consulting in research data management infrastructures. In the same year, the RDM policy was adopted at KIT to emphasize the topic of research data management. Other KIT departments joined the alliance of RDM experts in the following years.

Skills4EOSC CC Entry since

2025

Competences

- Research data management (RDM), FAIR principles, data management planning tools
- Open Access and Open Access repositories
- Research Data Repositories
- Training, consultation, knowledge building
- Coordination, networking, dissemination

- Legal and ethical questions in RDM, Open Access, Good Scientific Practice

Services offered

- RDM and OS training courses (also “on demand”)
- Support and advice (funding applications, Open Consultation hours etc.)
- Contact point for legal issues at RDM
- Guides, guidelines and good practices
- Community engagement events

2.3.10 Extending the Network beyond Europe

The Skills4EOOSC project and the activities developed for the benefit of the CC Network have attracted interest beyond the borders of the European Union. In particular, institutions from Tunisia and Turkey participated in the Network activities at different times during the project. In fact, the Tunisian Centre National Universitaire de Documentation Scientifique et Technique has actively participated in the Training the Trainers sessions and in the monthly CC meetings held since February 2025, and has shown interest in becoming a possible national centre of excellence. See below for more information on the Tunisian CC.

2.3.10.1 Centre National Universitaire de Documentation Scientifique et Technique

CNUDST [R12] is a governmental institution based in Tunisia whose main mission is to collect and publish Tunisian research results and make them visible locally and globally. CNUDST is considered a reference point for Tunisian researchers and provides an essential research service to various stakeholders (researchers, universities, research organisations, policy makers) involved in the scientific research process in Tunisia. Since 2011, CNUDST has been advocating the principles of Open Access and Open Science and has organised several regular events related to these principles. CNUDST is also engaged in some actions to promote and implement FAIR practices and to this end, the CNUDST team, with the support of the FAIR-impact project mentors, has developed a Tunisian national action

plan to promote and enable FAIR practices in Tunisia. The starting point of this action plan is to provide key competences to Tunisian stakeholders, covering the seven areas defined by the European Competence Framework for Researchers. The main idea of the CNUDST is to join the Skills4EOSC Network in order to create a new permanent service within the CNUDST that will provide Tunisian stakeholders with tools to acquire the necessary competences.

3 Network Coordination Structure

3.1 Governance Model

Establishing a robust governance model is essential for ensuring the effective coordination and long-term sustainability of the Skills4EOSC Competence Centres Network. This chapter outlines the structural framework governing the Network, detailing the roles, responsibilities, and membership criteria that define its operation. It describes the key decision-making bodies—namely, the General Assembly (hereafter GA) and the Presidency—as well as the processes for membership admission, rights and obligations of members and contributors, and the mechanisms for network coordination.

The governance model was defined in Milestone 7.5 [R13] as shown in the figure 1:

Fig. 1 – Proposed simplified governance structure of the CC Network

The proposed governance model ensures broad participation and strategic decision-making. The model is structured around several key components:

1. **General Assembly:** This is the primary representative body, with two representatives from each member organization. The General Assembly plays a crucial role in decision-making processes, ensuring wide representation across the network.
2. **Presidency:** A coordinating and supervisory body within the network, functioning as an equal member alongside other network entities, responsible for facilitating network-wide coordination and supporting the collective strategic direction.
3. **Competence Centres:** These are the core operational units that contribute to the network's activities and goals. They provide expertise, resources, and insights to drive the network's initiatives.
4. **Editorial Board:** Responsible for managing the evolution of best practices, standards, and information sharing within the network.
5. **Working Groups:** Specialized teams that focus on specific tasks, research, or implementation efforts in accordance with the outcomes of the Skills4EOSC project, e.g. User Support Network should become a working-group of the CC Network after the end of the project.

The governance model also includes interactions with other stakeholders, such as international projects, national and international organisations focused on Open Science practices, creating a dynamic and inclusive ecosystem. The relationship between these components is characterized by:

- Contribution from Competence Centres
- Decision-making through the General Assembly
- Appointment of leadership and board members
- Continuous evolution of practices and standards

After the end of the Skills4EOSC project, CC Network will no longer be bound to the framework of work-packages, tasks, deliverables and milestones of the project. It is most likely that these initial provisions outlined in project documentation and this deliverable will be further adapted by the members of the Network.

3.1.1 Membership Terms

3.1.1.1 Definition and Conditions

Membership is open to non-profit and/or public entities, who meet the following criteria:

- Demonstrated commitment to promoting and advancing Open Science and EOSC on a national or supra-national level as outlined in the Competence Centre Charter;
- Active support for the Mission and Objectives of the Skills4EOSC Competence Centres Network as outlined above.

Additional criteria may be specified in the Network's Internal Rules.

3.1.1.2 Rights and Obligations

Each Member Organisation is entitled to:

- Participate in and contribute to the General Assembly
- Propose and lead Network activities, committees, working groups, and task forces established by the GA
- Take part in all Network activities
- Use the Network logo on their websites and relevant materials

Each Member Organisation shall commit to:

- Actively contribute to furthering the Purpose and Objectives of the Network
- Promote the Network and its activities both externally and within their own organization
- Appoint a dedicated representative to the General Assembly as the main contact and liaison between the Network and the Member Organisation
- Comply with the provisions of the Network's Internal Rules and any established agreements

3.1.2 Other Contributor Types

Other legal entities or individuals are welcome to engage with the Skills4EOSC Network as contributors and/or supporters if they meet one of the following criteria:

- Open Science and/or EOSC Champions: Individuals actively involved in developing Open Science practices or making significant contributions to EOSC in Europe
- Skills4EOSC Network Affiliates: Non-profit and/or public research and/or research support structures with a strong interest in promoting and advancing Open Science and EOSC
- Network Partners: Networks, associations, and alliances active in any geographical areas that share the Purpose and Objectives of the Skills4EOSC Network as described above

Additional criteria may be specified in the Network's Internal Rules.

3.1.2.1 Rights and Obligations

Each contributor and/or supporter is entitled to:

- Participate in the General Assembly (without voting rights)
- Participate in the Network's activities
- Propose, lead and contribute to Network activities, committees, working groups, and task forces established by the GA
- Receive all member benefits of the Network, as detailed in the Network's internal rules
- Use the Network logo on their websites and on relevant materials

Each Contributor shall commit to:

- Actively contribute to furthering the purpose and objectives of the Network as established by the GA
- Promote the Network and its activities both externally and within their own organisation
- Appoint a dedicated representative that will act as the main contact and liaison between the Network and the member
- Respect the provisions of the internal rules

3.1.3 Terms of engagement

3.1.3.1 Admission of members

Admission of members to the network is delegated to the Presiding Competence Centre, provided that the candidate Competence Centre sends a Memorandum of Understanding (MoU)/Letter of Intent (LoI) signed by the duly authorised representative. MoU/LoI is a promissory document, outlining the commitment of the candidate Competence Centre, and should include specific contributions proposed.

Presiding Competence Centre may request any clarifications or additional information from the candidate Competence Centre in writing or invite candidate CC representatives to one or more meetings to discuss their membership.

Presiding Competence Centre informs the General Assembly representatives by the means of electronic communication of the candidacy and all additional clarifications and information received from the candidate Competence Centre.

Presiding Competence Centre will defer the decision to the General Assembly, if any objections arise from GA members within two weeks from the date of the initial information.

Presiding Competence Centre may also defer the decision to the GA if there are any uncleared uncertainties regarding the candidate Competence Centre.

In the case of deference, admission of member is automatically included in the agenda of the upcoming GA meeting provided that the decision to defer was made sufficiently in advance to provide the information on the matter in accordance with the terms of GA meetings.

Additional information may be requested from the candidate Competence Centre by the GA to clarify any uncertainties. Candidate Competence Centre representatives may be invited to the GA meeting to present their case. GA then decides whether to authorise or not the admission of the candidate Competence Centre.

Membership is confirmed in writing by the Presiding Competence Centre without unnecessary delay after all the uncertainties have been addressed.

Presiding Competence Centre has an authority to refuse a membership with or without deferring it to the GA in case of a failure to address the uncertainties, provide the additional information, or in cases where the candidate Competence Centre does not meet the criteria of the Competence Centre Charter. Presiding Competence Centre will inform the GA on such decision.

3.1.3.2 Suspension and expulsion of members

Suspension and expulsion of members of the CC Network are at the ultimate authority of the General Assembly.

At the current stage of planning of the Competence Centre Network such procedures are not considered in detail. The GA will have to discuss such matters and decide on an individual basis.

3.1.3.3 Admission of other contributors

Admission of other types of contributors is not restricted. Individuals who would like to contribute to the working groups are welcome to join mailing-lists and use open collaborative spaces to contribute to the Competence Centre Network.

The Competence Centre Network will keep a registry of other contributors, therefore an individual or an organisation wishing to be considered as a contributor will have to register and agree to the use of their data in this registry.

Any individual or organisation may be expunged from the registry of contributors or any mailing-list of the CC Network under the decision of General Assembly.

Presiding Competence Centre will report such decision to the Competence Centre concerned, which no longer meets the essential requirements to remain part of the network.

3.1.4 Organisation and coordination of the Network

The main bodies of the CC Network in charge for the governance are:

- The General Assembly
- The Presidency

The GA will support management, operations, and administration of the CC Network. Other additional, permanent or temporary, bodies such as working groups, task-forces or committees are foreseen and can be appointed by the GA and can be defined further in the Internal Rules.

In the following subsections, the above presented bodies will be described and the main responsibilities and actions will be exposed.

3.1.4.1 General Assembly

The GA is the policy-making and decision-making body. It is chaired by the President, or by another member as a deputy. The GA is composed by two representatives from every member having the right to vote. Among the activities and roles, the GA is in charge to establish strategic guidelines, financial objectives and any other directives for the internal management of the CC Network, including the adoption of Internal Rules for any dispute that may arise, and decide the opportune measures to be taken in case of serious facts threatening the continuity of the CC Network. The GA organises its activities according to a strategic plan and roadmap agreed by the Network.

Representatives such as Contributors, Supporters and other interested bodies have the right to attend the GA as observers, if invited, and to have their opinion heard on all voting matters in an advisory capacity. External expert can also be invited to provide information and advice.

Among the activities and roles, the GA is in charge to elect the Presidency and to decide on any legal and practical aspect of the activities concerning the CC Network.

3.1.4.2 Presidency

The Presidency is nominated by the General Assembly and is responsible for overseeing the entire operation of the CC Network. The Presidency is

assumed by a Competence Centre within the Network, represented by one of its two members who are part of the General Assembly. The Presidency serves a two-year term, which can be renewed once for an additional two years.

The President may appoint a deputy and has the following responsibilities:

- coordinating and representing the Network
- organizing the event calendar
- working with the General Assembly to establish the Network's agendas
- signing agreements (e.g. Letters of Intent, Memoranda of Understanding) on behalf of the Network.

3.2 Collaboration Framework

The Collaboration Framework of the Skills4EOSC CCNet is formalised through a Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) signed by the founding Competence Centres of the Network. This MoU defines the Network's governance structure (see section [3.1](#)) and identifies the main objectives of the collaboration, including:

- **Networking and Peer-Learning:** Facilitating collaboration, knowledge exchange, and best practice sharing among Competence Centres.
- **Training and Capacity Building:** Developing and delivering targeted training programmes and learning paths in Open Science, FAIR data principles, and digital research management.
- **Support for Research Organisations:** Assisting institutions lacking national infrastructure or expertise in Open Science.
- **Development and Evolution of Key Outputs:** Contributing to the maintenance and advancement of Skills4EOSC methodologies and resources, including participation in the Editorial Board and Working Groups.
- **Partnerships and Advocacy:** Promoting research integrity, supporting advocacy efforts, and identifying EU funding opportunities.
- **Collaboration with European and Global Organisations:** Establishing strategic partnerships with other entities committed to Open Science and EOSC.

- Publications and Position Papers: Collaborating on joint publications and statements to influence Open Science policies.
- Sustainability of Results: Ensuring long-term impact through continued development and use of Skills4EOSC outcomes.

After the initial setup, other Competence Centres can join the Network by signing a Letter of Intent (LoI), which expresses their alignment with the CCNet's mission and values.

The MoU is a broader agreement signed by both parties — the President of the CC Network and the Competence Centre — to formalize collaboration, while the LoI is signed only by the Competence Centre to express its intention to join the Network. A Competence Centre may later sign the MoU once its participation is consolidated.

Both the MoU and the LoI (see Annex 1 and 2) serve as a lightweight, non-binding framework for cooperation, enabling flexible collaboration and information exchange while preserving institutional autonomy. Both the MoU and the LoI are template documents that can be modified and adapted by the Competence Centre Network according to future needs and requirements.

3.3 Coordination Mechanisms

The establishment of a robust Coordination Mechanism is essential to ensure the effective collaboration and synchronization of activities within the Network of CCs. Since the beginning of the Skills4EOSC project, a systematic coordination approach was implemented through regular workshops and knowledge sharing.

The following sections outline the chronological development of the Network's coordination mechanisms and identify a combination of digital tools and regular interactions to ensure continuous alignment and engagement after the end of the Skills4EOSC project.

3.3.1 Initial Establishment and Public Launch

The formal introduction of the Skills4EOSC Competence Centres Network occurred on June 25 2024, through a public online launch event [R14]. This

milestone gathering introduced the concept of Competence Centres as collaborative entities and networks bringing together expertise in Open Science and data management. The launch event highlighted the CCs' role in connecting stakeholders to national and international Open Science programs and providing access points to networks focused on Open Science and FAIR research practices.

3.3.2 Network Sustainability Workshop in Berlin

On October 21 2024, the project organized a pivotal workshop in Berlin titled "Making the Competence Centres Network sustainable and enhanced" [R15]. This in-person event brought together CC representatives, project partners, and guests from related projects to address three fundamental aspects: ensuring the sustainability of the Competence Centre network, exploring how the network could better support individual Competence Centres, and enhancing the overall collaboration effectiveness. The workshop employed interactive breakout sessions covering network aspects and Competence Centre aspects including services offered, data stewardship curriculum integration, and individual CC sustainability.

3.3.3 Competence Centres Network Workshops Series

Throughout 2025, a series of regular workshops consolidated the Network's structure and activities. The first workshop held in February established a framework for ongoing collaboration, focusing on strategic goals and the role of CCs in adopting Skills4EOSC results. Representatives from established Competence Centres in various countries shared their experiences and current activities. The sustainability of the Network was a central topic, emphasizing the importance of securing resources and support beyond the project's lifetime.

The March workshop built upon these foundations by addressing training course updates, introducing hybrid and asynchronous learning models. A significant portion was dedicated to exploring the evolving relationship between Competence Centres and EOSC Nodes, producing valuable insights on building strong networks, developing national awareness, and empowering Open Science communities.

The workshop held in April expanded the focus to include discussions on User Support Networks and minimum viable skills necessary for Open Science practitioners. Updates from emerging Competence Centres in Poland, Turkey, and the Czech Republic demonstrated the Network's expansion across Europe.

The workshop scheduled for May will address aspects related to the network's governance model, in preparation for the first in-person General Assembly of the CCNet, which will take place on June 10 in Paris.

These workshops collectively advanced the Network's maturity by identifying common challenges, sharing best practices, and developing joint strategies for sustainability. The regular cadence of meetings fostered community building and established communication channels essential for the Network's long-term operation.

3.3.4 Final Event: Building a Sustainable Future Workshop

The coordination activities will culminate in the "Building a Sustainable Future for Open Science: Skills4EOSC Competence Centres Workshop" [R16] scheduled for June 10 2025, in Paris. This event represents the first official coordination meeting aimed at formalizing the Network structure beyond the project's conclusion. The workshop will focus on ensuring network sustainability, improving support mechanisms for individual CCs, and enhancing overall collaboration effectiveness.

This workshop will be followed by the Skills4EOSC final conference, "Building Capacity for Open Science" [R17] on June 11 2025, which will highlight project achievements and feature discussions on the strategic vision for Open Science skills and the role of Competence Centres in supporting research and training.

3.3.5 Enabling Effective Communication Among Competence Centres

The following proposed Coordination Mechanism is designed to facilitate efficient internal communication, promote knowledge exchange, and drive joint initiatives among CCs that are part of the Network. It leverages a

combination of digital tools and regular interactions to ensure continuous alignment and engagement. Key components of this mechanism include:

- **Network Tools for Internal Coordination:** A set of online platforms and collaborative tools has been identified and could be utilized to streamline communication and document sharing among CCs, ensuring accessibility and transparency.
- **Mailing List:** A dedicated mailing list will serve as a primary communication channel for sharing updates, discussing key topics, and coordinating activities in a timely manner. The mailing list ccnetwork@lists.skills4eosc.eu was set up by GARR through its internal application in April 2024, on the occasion of the public launch of the CC Network. At the time of writing this Deliverable, the list includes 56 subscribers, all affiliated with the Competence Centres that are part of the Network. The mailing list will continue to be maintained by GARR even after the end of the project.
- **Monthly or Bi-Monthly Meetings:** Regular virtual meetings will be held to provide updates on ongoing initiatives, address challenges, and identify opportunities for collaboration.
- **Joint Workshops:** The CCs Network will organize and participate in joint workshops to foster knowledge exchange, develop shared strategies, and engage with the broader EOSC and Open Science community.
- **Position Papers on Open Science and CCs:** Collaborative efforts will be undertaken to draft and publish position papers addressing critical issues in Open Science and the evolving role of CCs, providing thought leadership and advocacy within the OS ecosystem.

3.4 Alignment Strategies for Key Outputs

The Skills4EOSC project has produced several key outputs that contribute to the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) skills ecosystem, including the Minimum Viable Skillsets (MVS), the FAIR-by-design methodology, and various training materials, summarised as “Open Science Skills Publications”. To ensure the sustainability and wider adoption of these resources, this chapter considers how an Editorial Board would operate as an alignment mechanism for the key outputs of Skills4EOSC and its scope within the Competence Centres Network.

The Editorial Board is conceived as a governance body responsible for ensuring strategic alignment and quality assurance across the various outputs produced by the project. By establishing consistent standards and review procedures, the Editorial Board will create coherence among the Skills4EOSC resources and enhance their value to the European Open Science community.

The starting point is the opportunity for the CC Network to establish a journal devoted to Open Science Skills. This could invite submission of methodological or pedagogical articles that guide EOSC skills development, including experiences developing skillsets for particular target groups and communities.

3.4.1 Value of an Open Science Skills Journal and Editorial Board

The establishment of an Open Science Skills Journal overseen by a dedicated Editorial Board would deliver substantial benefits to the CC Network and broader EOSC community. By creating a formal publication channel for Skills4EOSC outputs, the Journal would provide the wider community with structured means to engage with resources for building open science skills. This engagement pathway is essential for ensuring that the project's resources achieve their intended impact and continue to evolve in response to community needs. In the long-term, the journal establishes an opportunity to position the network as a go-to source for training and other skills development resources, creating a sustainable legacy beyond the project's duration. For CCs staff, the Journal offers a valuable mechanism to monitor community developments and gain professional recognition for their contributions to the Open Science Skills Landscape. Perhaps most importantly, the Editorial Board and the associated Journal would serve to articulate and disseminate the strategic vision of both the Network and individual Competence Centres, ensuring alignment with broader EOSC objectives.

3.4.2 Key Assumptions

The 'Open Science Skills Publications' have each been collectively authored, reviewed, and published as project deliverables, i.e. shared as 'grey

literature' reports in a public repository (Zenodo). In several cases (FAIR-by-Design and MVS), the repository record is linked to a dynamic git repository for versioning purposes.

To encourage uptake, articles describing the development and application of the MVS, FbD methodology, and courses could be submitted for journal publication. However OER repositories are the more appropriate outlet for courses, and there are various existing resources focused on sharing Open Science learning resources with appropriate metadata.

MVS do not fit match current forms of scholarly output, although they are close to competence frameworks in their distinguishing characteristics, which are:

- Focused on describing learning outcomes for one or more target groups, aiming to inform the design of courses or other forms of skills development.
- Linked 'upstream' to policies that set out higher-level objectives, and 'downstream' to course curricula and learning resources.
- Linked to ontologies and cited source materials.

MVS are conceived as 'minimum viable' products designed to be adapted to local needs. Even on that basis it seems likely that there will be multiple MVS for any given role or target group, as each Competence Centre will have stakeholders at national, regional, thematic, and disciplinary levels, whose policies shape the roles and their responsibilities. Zenodo and other repositories may be used to make MVS accessible in all their variety. However it is also important to communicate why different target groups and communities vary in their essential skills, or in how these skills are being acquired. In this context, a journal could serve as a valuable outlet for short, focused articles that reference the MVS and other relevant resources.

3.4.2.1 Editorial Board Functions

The level of control exercised by an Editorial Board would therefore include the following elements:

- Templates for each kind of output

- Quality criteria tailored to each output type
- Ethical guidelines for the review process
- Submission policies and procedures
- Review procedures

The scope and content of these could initially be quite generic. Model policies for journal editing are readily available, and there is extensive expertise in scholarly publication available within Skills4EOSC and the CC Network. Models for publishing learning paths are available e.g. from ELIXIR. The Carpentries 'incubator' model could also be considered, although possibly as a longer-term option.

A key assumption is that the CC Network would receive input on the overall needs for EOSC skills development through the EOSC Association and the European Commission, whose reports and funding calls will provide guidance on the types of occupations to be targeted, and the high-level learning outcomes to be pursued. The roles that Skills4EOSC targeted for developing the MVS were initially informed by the EOSC Executive Working Group report on Digital Skills for FAIR and Open Science, while the outcomes were informed by the Horizon Europe Programme Guide. Similar input might be provided by, for example, the EOSC-A Opportunity Area Expert Group 'Skills, Training, Rewards, Recognition & Upscaling' and its outputs.

3.4.3 Future Development of the Editorial Board

It is important to note that this chapter presents only a preliminary outline of the Editorial Board structure. The detailed responsibilities, operational rules, and specific tasks of the Editorial Board will be further defined in the near future, as the project progresses. Working groups will be established to develop comprehensive terms of reference, membership criteria, and decision-making procedures that ensure appropriate representation across the Competence Centre Network.

The proposed Editorial Board structure will be formally presented in Paris, on the 10th of June 2025, at the upcoming "Building a Sustainable Future for Open Science: Skills4EOSC Competence Centres Workshop" (see R16). During this event, the CC Network framework will be discussed with representatives

across the Competence Centre Network, in order to gather feedback and refine the approach. The final proposal will then be submitted for approval during the General Assembly that will take place at the same event. This collaborative approach to establishing the Editorial Board ensures that it will reflect the diverse needs and perspectives of the entire Network while providing effective governance for Open Science Skills Publications.

3.5 Join the CCs Network: how to

During the lifetime of the Skills4EOSC project, to support the new CCs and facilitate their establishment, key elements and aspects have been identified as depicted in the Figure 2 below.

Each organisation can provide the required information using an interactive web form clicking the button “Try now” [R18] that will guide them through this process. Once all the form fields are completed, the user can submit it and a PDF of the answers will be generated. You can then send this PDF to the email address provided to submit your application.

After the project ends, this guide will remain available on the website for approximately three years. After that period, the guidelines can be transferred to the CC network, ensuring its continued accessibility and dissemination within the community.

The terms of engagement, the criteria for admission and the procedure for becoming a member of the CC Network after the end of the Skills4EOSC project were described in sections 3.1.3 and 3.2.

3.5.1 Guidelines for the new CC creation

This section outlines the essential guidelines and best practices for establishing a new Competence Centre (CC), providing a structured approach to ensure alignment with the Network's objectives. A dedicated webpage [R19] on the Skills4EOSC website serves as a comprehensive guide for organisations aiming to establish a Competence Centre (CC) under the Skills4EOSC initiative. The guidelines outline a step-by-step approach to setting up a CC as showed in Figure 2.

Fig.2 - Steps to consider when establishing a National/Thematic CC

4 Technical Infrastructure and Services

Skills4EOSC Competence Centres rely on diverse tools and technologies for accomplishing their specific missions and goals and providing their designated community with envisaged services. The document "D7.2 Sample of services toolset: a practical guideline" [R20] describes a minimal set of tools and technologies that have proven to be effective in helping Skills4EOSC Competence Centres achieve their specific goals. A brief summary of these tools is given below.

4.1 Selected IT Services Overview

The tools discussed in D7.2 are categorized into four main classes:

- Tools and solutions for training management, which CC developers can use to offer online courses to their communities. These tools include Moodle (largely used by Competence Centres), BigBlueButton, and Jitsi;
- Tools and solutions for collaborative work, designed to create collaborative working environments for their designated community. These tools include among others ONLYOFFICE and Nextcloud as office suites, Mattermost as collaboration platform, and Zulip as communication platform.
- Tools and solutions for publishing, which enable CC developers to provide access to content and materials for their communities. These tools include DSpace and Dataverse as repositories, Catalogue as-a-Service as platform for collaboratively developing community-driven catalogues, and Open Journal Systems as platform for developing open journals.
- Tools and solutions for virtual laboratories, which allow CC developers to create environments where users can engage with real services, including cloud-based options. These tools include virtual research environments and data management plan platforms.

This set of tools is accompanied by a set of recommendations concerning tools selection:

- Open Source and Interoperability: Prioritize open-source tools that comply with open standards for flexibility and sustainability. Ensure they support

interoperability by adhering to data formats, metadata, and API standards for seamless integration with other systems, including EOSC services.

- **Scalability and Flexibility:** Select tools that can adapt to growing needs and varying workloads. Choose solutions with modular designs, capable of addressing diverse user needs, from novices to expert researchers.
- **Security and Data Protection:** Opt for tools with strong security features like encryption and access controls, ensuring compliance with GDPR and relevant data protection regulations, especially for personal or sensitive data.
- **User Experience and Accessibility:** Focus on user-friendly tools with intuitive interfaces and comprehensive documentation, while also including accessibility features to cater to varied user needs.
- **Adherence to FAIR Data Principles:** Ensure tools facilitate the creation and management of FAIR data, using persistent identifiers and standardised metadata for clear licensing and reuse.
- **Deployment Models:** Consider self-hosted solutions for greater control and security, third-party hosted services for reduced maintenance, or a hybrid approach that combines self-hosting for core services with outsourcing supplementary tools for optimal flexibility.

4.2 Shared Services Portfolio

The current settings driving Competence Centres development and operation haven't led to shared services. In essence, every Competence Centre developed its own agenda concerning services to be offered. This agenda takes into account several characteristics, including the designated community, the availability of funding and expertise, and the operational settings of each CC.

When thinking in terms of a Coordinated Network of Competence Centres it is paramount to take shared decisions concerning the expected services and the acquisition, deployment and operation strategies. Moreover, the operation of the coordinated network is expected to rely on (a) *core services* that enable the network to function and (b) *additional services* whose

identification and extent depend on several factors that are expected to be decided by the CCNet governance (cf. Sec. 3).

Concerning the core services, they have been identified in Section 3 and mainly consist of services and tools that support the coordination of the network, along with one dedicated service to provide web presence for the CCNet (a CCNet website or gateway), its activities and results. The services and tools envisaged to support the User Support Network (cf. Sec. 5) should also be part of the core services of the CCNet.

Concerning the additional services, they are expected to be identified when the CCNet will be formally established. These services can either be conceived as *CCNet services*, i.e. conceptually centralised services operated by the CCNet for the needs of the CCNet as a whole, or *CCNet replicated services*, i.e. service instances each deployed to support the needs of a CC of the network. An example of both typologies is a catalogue of training material. The CCNet can consider to set up and operate an aggregative catalogue collecting training material from all the catalogues of training materials operated by the CCs of the CCNet. On their turn, each CC of the network is provided with its own catalogue by relying on a replica of the same service.

Some services are expected to be there as a result of, or with the support of, EOSC. The development of the EOSC Federation promises both the availability of a rich array of services ready to use and reuse, as well as the provision of services and tools that facilitate interoperability. The CCNet service portfolio can grow by leveraging EOSC service offer, as well as because of the need to support interoperability with the EOSC Federation.

4.3 Service Evolution Strategy

The service evolution strategy aims at managing and guiding the continuous improvement and interoperability of the services within the CCNet and ensuring the alignment of these with user needs and governance policies. The short-term and long-term roadmap, as well as the roles and responsibilities, driving the CCNet service evolution will be defined by the

CCNet governance. This strategy will take into account input from federation members and end users, as well as new opportunities and evolutions resulting from emerging technologies and services, and requirements to maintain compliance with regulatory frameworks like GDPR and FAIR principles.

5 User Support Network

5.1 Definition

The User Support Network [R21] is a strategic initiative designed within the Skills4EOSC project to facilitate the adoption of open science practices. User support activities carried out within research infrastructures, or computing and data centres, play a fundamental role in the research production life cycle, and therefore can become an essential actor in promoting open science practices.

These activities cover the entire science workflow, ranging from access to computing and data resources, definition and implementation of algorithms and tools, including FAIR data management, adoption of high level techniques such as AI, up to the delivery of scientific results.

The Skills4EOSC User Support Network (USN) was initially established through the involvement of interested teams already providing user support for their connected users and communities.

Subsequently, the USN aims to expand, by opening the participation of additional centres with the goal to promote a supportive ecosystem where researchers and research staff can seek help, advice, and guidance to overcome challenges in specialised fields, both directly and indirectly related to Open Science.

The main goals of the USN initiative can be summarised as follows:

- Collecting information, experiences and best practices between members and sharing them within the USN members and with external actors interested in creating their own User Support Channel (USC);
- Fostering cooperation links between the USN members of the network;
- Promoting activities in thematic fields to provide resources and training;
- Creating a platform for sharing resources, knowledge and experiences

As agreed in the USN initiative, it is up to the USN members to define how the network is structured and which activities are important. As an example,

the cross-border knowledge exchange has been recognised as one of the means to facilitate the exchange of information about research endeavours, on-premises cloud computing resources, and specialised services among USN members. This cross-border knowledge sharing enhances understanding, enabling USN members and related teams to broaden their expertise and learn from best practices across the network.

The activities, and their benefits, considered to be important from the network members have been hereafter identified. The activities carried out by the USN initiative will be described in Section [5.4](#).

- *Knowledge sharing:*
 - Activities: Dedicated repository, online forums, and documentation to share information among the network members.
 - Benefits: USC members gain access to a wealth of expertise.
- *Training and Skills Development:*
 - Activities: Collaboration to organise specialised training programs on the services provided by the USC, e.g., AI, HPC ,etc.
 - Benefits: USC members enhance their team's skills, staying at the forefront of advancements in AI and HPC, etc.
- *Collaborative Projects and Resource Sharing:*
 - Activities: Fostering the collaboration among USCs on the respective topics, projects, sharing of best practices, and resources.
 - Benefits: Promoting the engagement in collaborative projects, leveraging shared resources, and expanding the network of collaborators.
- *Sharing EOSC Projects materials :*
 - Activities: The Skills4EOSC project will share materials on FAIR-by-Design Template Implementation: how to create FAIR learning materials, e.g. courses, trainings etc. in practice. Other projects are welcome to share their outcomes if relevant.
 - Benefits: USC members that offer trainings can use these materials to enhance their existing or new training materials to be more FAIR, thus enabling accessibility and discoverability of their resources.

Sharing project outcomes also supports the broader use and exploitation of the materials, while helping members stay informed about advancements and best practices in their field of reference.

5.2 User Support Channels

The members of the User Support Network represent various teams providing support at different levels and with different scopes in their institutions; these groups are named User Support Channels or USCs and a member can be part or contribute to an already existing Competence Center node (see Figure 3 for a graphical representation of the the USN integration within the Skills4EOSC project).

More specifically, User Support Channels, either formally or informally structured, are groups of experts who provide direct support at technical, operational or consultancy levels to researchers within a specific community, infrastructure, service or resource. These include:

- Specific computing resources, such as cloud and HPC services or specialised resources such as GPUs
- Tools to access or publish data such as data repositories or open access journals
- Artificial Intelligence tools or applications tailored to researchers' specific needs
- USCs usually provide training to their target users and they may also operate help-desks, providing a means to share best practices and experience, encouraging interdisciplinary activity, and promoting a wide collaboration.

The USCs, along with their related descriptions, activities and reference target communities, are listed in Table 1.

Figure 3: USC and their interaction in the Skills4EOSC project

Table 1: list of the active USCs and short description

USC	Short description	Weblink	Services offered	Target communities
EGI Federation	EGI or EGI Federation is one of the largest distributed computing infrastructures for data-intensive research collaborations. It federates hundreds of major research data centres in Europe and worldwide, making advanced computing services, capacity and research data accessible in a federated manner to members of international scientific collaborations. The EGI Federation	https://egi.eu/	To facilitate the technical integration of scientific use cases in the distributed and federated infrastructure, EGI has a dedicated team of supporters consisting of experts that provide first-line of technical support to help scientific communities to integrate with the advanced solutions offered by the EGI ecosystem. From a technical point of view, technical support is provided via helpdesk and face-to-face fashion.	Communities that deal with challenges in managing and analysing big scientific datasets. They can be in any scientific discipline, and from both academia and industry.

	provides access to more than 1.2 Exabyte of research data and 1.2 Million CPU Cores for data processing and analysis needs to thousands of researchers.			
Karlsruhe Institute of Technology	Product Owner of the Helpdesk	https://www.scc.kit.edu/	Delivery of the EOSC EU Node Helpdesk to EC and to research communities	EOSC, NFDI, eu research communities
GRNET - National Infrastructures for Research and Technology / Infrastructures and projects directorate	The HPC support team is responsible for the operation of the HPC system, user and applications support, handling of user accounts, compute budget allocations, reports, collection and review of applications for access, training etc. In addition, since GRNET acts as a hub between academia and research institutes, it is in contact with scientists, researchers and academic staff who have the skills and are willing to be involved in various actions.	https://www.hpc.grnet.gr/en/	HPC infrastructure and user support	Academia and research institutes
Fondazione ICSC - Centro Nazionale di Ricerca in High Performance	The Center conducts R&D, nationally and internationally, for innovation in high-performance computing, simulations, and big	https://www.supercomputing-icsc.it/	The National Supercomputing Centre will be a distributed and transversal infrastructure with the mission of	High energy physics, national infrastructure users, etc

ce Computing , Big Data e Quantum Computing	data analytics. This aim is pursued through a state-of-the-art infrastructure for high-performance computing and big data management, which leverages existing resources and integrates emerging technologies, and an organization and distribution of activities based on the Hub and Spoke model.		supporting the world of scientific research and the business world for the innovation and digitization of the country	
Stefan Roiser, CERN Staff	Computer scientist working on performance software engineering for high energy physics simulation applications. Involved in several training activities including the leading of the "Training and Recognition" work package of the EOSC/EVERSE project.		Training for research software engineering e.g. through EVERSE	Research software engineers in high energy physics and natural sciences in general
INFN Open Science group	INFN group: consolidated knowledge and expertise in the framework of data management, open science, FAIR principles, computer programming, DMP drafting.	n.a.	Information and know-how exchange in the framework of FAIR principles, DMP drafting, setting up of a repository based on invenio rdm	Physics, national infrastructure users
HPC Serbia	HPC Serbia is EuroCC2's national competence center	https://www.hpc.rs/	Support to end-users who require assistance with using	Industry, academia, and public

	for High-Performance Computing (HPC).		HPC, HPDA, and AI resources in their daily activities.	administration.
Open Science Lab	The Open Cloud Research Lab is the largest open research e-Infrastructure in the state that has just started with its work. Its services are offered to all researchers in the country and it is supported by a team from the computing center at the Ss. Cyril and Methodius University in Skopje.	https://osc-lab.finki.ukim.mk/en	Access and use of GPGPU cluster, Openstack cloud, and Data storage	researchers, national infrastructure users

5.3 Services for the User Support Network

To support the USN initiative, different services have been made available by the USN participants.

- USN Repository to share documents and materials:
 - Hosted by Google (consumer, provided by INFN) and available via [R22].
 - Different thematic sections available to store material and documents.
- USN Mattermost communication Channel
 - Provided by KIT and available [R23]
 - Different thematic sections available to store material and documents.
- USN mailing list
 - For communication: usnetwork@lists.skills4eosc.eu
- USN Conferences and meetings
 - Zoom application provided by INFN

- Guide on how to use the above mentioned services
 - Available in the USN repository [\[R24\]](#)

5.4 Activities and Materials

The USN initiative formally started in September 2024 with the organisation of a dedicated Kick-off meeting. The event, held online, saw the participation of about 40 interested people coming from 24 different institutions across Europe.

The agenda is available [\[R25\]](#). As indicated in the agenda, representatives from 8 USCs presented their user support and training activities, including best practices, technologies adopted and possible topics for collaboration. The materials include a presentation on the USN initiative, goals and objective, and are made available in the agenda and in the USN repository.

Other activities that have been organised and carried out are described hereafter:

- May 2024 - 1st Webinar: Skills4EOSC User Support Network [\[R26\]](#)
The online webinar focused on the presentation of the USN initiative and the plans to define and prepare the aforementioned USN Kick-off meeting. The event was attended by 20 people from different institutions. The materials have been made available in the agenda and in the USN repository.
- November 2024 - Skills4EOSC User Support Network - 2nd Meeting [\[R27\]](#)
This online event focused on the presentation of the Italian Research Center on HPC, Big Data and Quantum Computing and on the definition of the expertise and requirements of the USCs, with an analysis of their different needs. The event was attended by 15 participants from various institutions. The materials are available in the agenda and the USN repository.
- January 2025 - Skills4EOSC User Support Network - 3rd Meeting [\[R28\]](#)
This online event focused on the presentation of the Best practices adopted within the Open Science Lab followed by a related discussion among USCs about the interest in participating. The event saw the participation of 15

people from different institutions. The materials have been made available in the agenda and in the USN repository.

- March 2025 - Skills4EOSC User Support Network - 4th Meeting [\[R29\]](#)
The online event centered on showcasing User support and training initiatives within the INFN DataCloud, followed by discussions among USCs regarding participation interest. Ten individuals from various institutions attended the event. All materials were shared through both the agenda and the USN repository.
- Other activities included the promotion by the USCs of the USN initiative in different meetings.

A description of the USN initiative have been made available on the Skills4EOSC website [\[R30\]](#). On this page, a video has been created and made available, describing the USN initiative, some relevant use cases and the benefits that participants can gain by joining the USN initiative. As an integral part of the USN initiative, a USN Application Form [\[R31\]](#) has been prepared and made available via the EUSurvey [\[R32\]](#) service. The form has been distributed among the USCs and other interested people, with the aim to collect information related to current activities, interest and contact points. The data extracted from the survey have been analysed to gather the information needed to contact and engage individuals interested to the USN initiative.

6 CC Network Sustainability Strategy

The CC Network Sustainability strategy has been addressed in the work of Task 5 within WP7. The Task has completed the analysis of the sustainability of project outputs. It has been based on the Business Model Canvas (BMC) adapted to the setup of the community working on the Skills4EOOSC project, as well as to the likely post-project setup. The BMC was modified to reflect the reality of the “value network”, where the members of the network are main beneficiaries (clients) of the network as a whole.

The strategy to sustain the outcomes of the project is based on keeping the community alive and expanding, and thus keeping the project outcomes evolving in accordance with the required value by community members. The Competence Centre Network serves as a lightweight organisational structure to ensure the continuation and evolution of the community. The sustainability analysis, documented in the milestone report MS 7.5 ([see R13](#)), outlines the roadmap to achieve the organisational setup before the end of the project. Competence Centre Network will be ready to undertake the delivery of the value of Skills4EOOSC outputs.

To achieve sustainability, a number of steps have been identified to be implemented until the end of the project. The organisational structure and procedures for the acceptance of new members, as well as general decision-making within the Competence Centre Network are essential parts of sustainability ([see section 3](#)).

Figure 4: Essential steps to ensure the sustainability of Skills4EOSC outputs

Deliverable D7.4 ‘Guidelines for sustainability of the network of Competence Centres’ will provide a detailed analysis and report on the progress of the outlined steps up to the date of the publication.

The analysis of the sustainability of the Skills4EOSC Project outcomes has been based on the assumption that the value of the project outcomes ensure their evolution and support of the community at least in a short term, lasting 1-2 years after the end of the project. This approach will require a dedicated effort from community members, both in terms of allocating human resources as well as some infrastructure resources. Long-term sustainability, evolution, and maximisation of impact of the project outcomes may require additional funding on national, regional and pan-European level. These options were analysed in the work of Task 8.3. There is a number of potential relevant initiatives to explore for the longer-term funding of efforts and resources to maximise the value proposition to members of the Competence

Centre Network. Most of the potential instruments are a national level funding, indicating the demand for advancing the knowledge of EOSC and Open Science in general. It offers opportunities for Competence Centres to exploit the value of the outcomes of the Skills4EOSC project, while providing their contributions as resources to the Network generating synergies.

Figure 5: Number of funding instruments analysed in 8.3 by the level of funding

Moreover, there are some possible options of joint organisational effort especially within the federated framework of EOSC Nodes. This environment is still evolving at the time of this sustainability analysis. These topics are considered as part of a future discussion on sustainability, that will continue until the end of the project and will have to extend well beyond the end of the project.

7 Recommendations

Based on the Competence Centres Network and User Support Network monthly meetings held in 2025, several recommendations for the evolution of Competence Centres, User Support Channels and their Networks have been identified and reported in the following sections.

7.1 For Existing and New CCs

- Strengthen the training role through the identification and development of master trainers who can replicate courses in their local communities.
- Invest in training infrastructures, such as online platforms and repositories, to ensure continuous support for researchers and institutions.
- Expand the portfolio of services offered, going beyond training to include policy consultation and technical support for Open Science.
- Develop national networks to strengthen the Open Science ecosystem, facilitating connections between research communities and EOSC nodes.
- Pursue sustainable funding models, combining national funds, institutional support, and project-based funding.
- Integrate Open Science training into university curricula, as already done in North Macedonia with doctoral programs.
- Collaborate with national Ministries of Education to obtain recognition as centres of excellence.
- Develop training materials following the "FAIR-by-Design Methodology" to ensure openness and accessibility.

7.2 For Existing and New USCs and USN

As described in [Section 5.1](#), the list of possible activities and their benefits to the network members have to be explored and maintained by leveraging the services made available for the USN initiative. However, the sustainability of the USN initiative is left to the individuals and it can be established only if periodic interactions among the USCs are maintained and common interests are adequately prompted and stimulated, such as:

- Standardize Knowledge Management - Leveraging on the Skills4EOSC project outcomes, create a centralized, searchable knowledge base that consolidates solutions, best practices, and expertise across all USCs to prevent knowledge silos and reduce duplicate efforts
- Enhance Cross-Channel Collaboration - Facilitate regular knowledge exchange sessions between different USCs to share domain-specific expertise
- Formalise Training Programs - Develop a comprehensive training curriculum for both USC staff and end-users with certification paths to ensure consistent quality of support across all channels
- Integrate Communication Platforms - Consolidate the various communication tools (Mattermost, mailing lists, repository) into a more cohesive ecosystem that maintains historical knowledge while improving accessibility
- Expand User Feedback Mechanisms - Implement systematic user feedback collection at multiple touchpoints to continuously improve services based on researcher needs and evolving technological landscapes

7.3 For CC Network Evolution

- Clearly define the relationship with EOSC nodes, potentially operating on parallel but complementary tracks, respecting diverse national situations
- Consider onboarding the entire Skills4EOSC Network as a service/resource within the EOSC Federation
- Implement monthly meetings to ensure regular updates and continuous engagement among participants
- Harmonise training and knowledge sharing through a common training catalogue
- Support new Competence Centres with technical support and sharing of best practices
- Facilitate the exchange and dissemination of Open Science services among national communities to strengthen the EOSC framework

- Strengthen communication and collaboration among Competence Centres to ensure long-term success
- Explore contribution to the EU EOSC Training Catalogue through sharing training resources developed by Network members

Annex 1 - Memorandum of Understanding

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Coordination network for the Skills4EOSC Competence Centres and Support Centres Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) Template

This Memorandum of Understanding (hereinafter referred to as “MoU”) is entered into between the **Skills4EOSC Competence Centres Network (CCNet)** and **[Competence Centre Name]** (hereinafter referred to as “the Parties”), with the purpose of formalizing their intention to collaborate and foster cooperation in Open Science.

Introduction of the Parties

The **Skills4EOSC Competence Centre Network (CCNet)** is a collaborative network of national, regional, and thematic Competence Centres across Europe and beyond, supporting Open Science practices. Initially established under the EU-funded **Horizon Europe Skills4EOSC** project, CCNet connects organizations and experts in Open Science, FAIR data principles, and digital research management. The network promotes knowledge exchange, provides community-specific support, and ensures the sustainability and evolution of Skills4EOSC project outputs through contributions of its members to the **Editorial Board** and **specialized Working Groups**.

[Competence Centre Name] is a **[brief description of the Competence Centre's mission, activities, and expertise]**, committed to advancing Open Science and contributing to the EOOSC ecosystem in **[Country/Region/Theme]**.

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Objectives and Scope of Cooperation

This MoU signifies the intention of the Parties to establish a collaborative relationship in the following areas for their mutual benefit:

- **Networking and Peer-Learning:** Facilitating collaboration, knowledge exchange, and best practice sharing among Competence Centres.
- **Training and Capacity Building:** Developing and delivering targeted training programs and learning paths in Open Science, FAIR data principles, and digital research management.
- **Support for Research Organizations:** Providing assistance to research organizations lacking national infrastructure or expertise in Open Science.
- **Development and Evolution of Key Outputs:** Contributing to the continuous development, maintenance, and adoption of Skills4EOSC methodologies, including participation in the Editorial Board and Working Groups.
- **Partnerships and Advocacy:** Promoting research integrity, supporting advocacy efforts, and identifying EU funding opportunities.
- **Collaboration with European and Global Organizations:** Building strategic partnerships with other entities committed to Open Science and EOSC.
- **Publications and Position Papers:** Engaging in joint publications and statements to influence Open Science policies.
- **Sustainability of Results:** Ensuring the ongoing impact of the Skills4EOSC project by maintaining and further developing its results.

Governance and Representation

The Skills4EOSC CCNet operates through a collaborative governance model comprising:

- **General Assembly:** Composed of two representatives from each Competence Centre, serving as the main decision-making body.
- **Presidency:** Led by a representative from a member Competence Centre, responsible for chairing the Network, acting as the primary point of contact, and ensuring effective coordination.
- **Editorial Board:** Overseeing the development, maintenance, and dissemination of Skills4EOSC outputs.
- **Specialized Working Groups:** Addressing specific challenges and initiatives within the Open Science landscape.

The **Skills4EOSC Competence Centre Charter**¹ outlines the general criteria for joining CCNet. Upon signing this MoU, [**Competence Centre Name**] will nominate two representatives to participate in the General Assembly.

Administrative and Legal Considerations

¹ See at <https://zenodo.org/records/10048176>

- This MoU is not a legally binding document. It represents the Parties' good-faith intention to collaborate. This notwithstanding, the Parties jointly represent that they will apply any reasonable means and efforts towards fulfilling the provisions below.
- **[Competence Centre Name]** undertakes to contribute the necessary resources including time of their staff, necessary budgets for travel and subsistence in order to ensure the **[Competence Centre Name]** participation as a member, as well as representation of the community.
- In respect of any information or materials supplied by one Party to another under the CCNet, be it by granting access to electronic resources or otherwise (jointly referred to as '**Access Rights**'), no warranty or representation of any kind is made, given or implied as to the sufficiency or fitness for purpose nor as to the absence of any infringement of any proprietary rights of third parties. Therefore, the recipient Party shall in all cases be entirely and solely liable for the use to which it puts such information and materials. No Party granting Access Rights shall be liable in case of infringement of proprietary rights of a third party resulting from any other Party (or its entities under the same control) exercising its Access Rights.
- No Party shall be responsible to any other Party for any indirect or consequential loss or similar damage such as, but not limited to, loss of profit, loss of revenue, or loss of contracts. A Party's liability shall not be limited under the foregoing paragraphs to the extent such damage was caused by a wilful act or gross negligence or to the extent that such limitation is not permitted by law.
- Each Party shall be solely liable for any loss, damage, or injury to third parties resulting from the performance of the said Party's obligations by it or on its behalf under this MoU or from its use of Results or Background.
- The Parties shall endeavour to settle any disputes amicably. If such a dispute cannot be resolved, the courts of Brussels shall have exclusive jurisdiction.
- The signatories of the two Parties will maintain regular contact to discuss any managerial matters related to the cooperation described in this MoU or to be integrated into it.
- Each Party will maintain full responsibility for its own activities.

Nomination of Representatives

[Competence Centre Name] hereby nominates the following two representatives to participate in the General Assembly of the Skills4EOSC Competence Centres Network:

- [Full Name of Representative 1], [Role/Position/Contact Email]
- [Full Name of Representative 2], [Role/Position/Contact Email]

These representatives shall serve as the official delegates of **[Competence Centre Name]** in all matters pertaining to the General Assembly.

Duration

This MoU shall enter into force on the date of signature and will remain valid for four years, unless otherwise agreed upon by the Parties.

Signatures

For the Skills4EOSC Competence Centres Network (CCNet)

[Name and Title]

Representative of the Presidency of the Network

Email: **[Contact Email]**

Address: **[Institution Address]**

Website: **[Institution Website]**

Signature: _____

Date: _____

For the Competence Centre Name

[Name and Title]

Email: **[Contact Email]**

Address: **[Institution Address]**

Website: **[Institution Website]**

Signature: _____

Date: _____

Annex 2 - Letter of Intent

Supporting EOSC

Letter of Intent (LoI) to join the Skills4EOSC Competence Centres Network (CCNet)

[Place], [Date]

To the President of the Skills4EOSC Competence Centres Network (CCNet),

We, [**Competence Centre Name**], hereby express our intent to join the Skills4EOSC Competence Centres Network (CCNet) and to actively contribute to its mission and collaborative framework.

[**Competence Centre Name**] is a [brief description of the organisation and its mission, activities, or role in Open Science, e.g.: "national centre focused on training, policy support, and infrastructure for Open Science and FAIR data in XYZ country"].

By signing this Letter of Intent, [**Competence Centre Name**] confirms its alignment with the principles and participation criteria outlined in the Skills4EOSC Competence Centre Charter², and commits to the collaborative objectives of the Network. In particular, we agree to:

- Facilitate knowledge exchange and peer-learning among Competence Centres;
- Co-develop and deliver training programmes and capacity-building activities in Open Science and data stewardship;
- Support research organisations lacking Open Science infrastructure or expertise;

² See at <https://zenodo.org/records/10048176>

- Contribute to the development and maintenance of the Skills4EOSC key outputs through participation in Working Groups and/or the Editorial Board;
- Engage in joint advocacy, dissemination, and publication efforts to promote Open Science and FAIR practices;
- Allocate the necessary internal resources, including staff time and travel budget, to ensure effective participation in CCNet activities.

Nomination of Representatives

In accordance with the CCNet governance model, we hereby nominate the following two representatives to serve as our official delegates in the General Assembly:

1. [Full Name], [Role/Title], [Email Address]
2. [Full Name], [Role/Title], [Email Address]

We look forward to a constructive collaboration within the CCNet and to contributing to a strong and sustainable European Open Science community.

Sincerely,

[Full Name of the Signatory]

[Position]

[Competence Centre Name]

Signature

Email

References

No	Description/Link
R1	Lazzeri, E., Di Giorgio, S., Lines, C., Gingold, A., Gaido, L., Prnjat, O., Sharma, C., Berberi, L., Candela, L., Schirru, L., Karla, A., & Irakleitos, S. (2023). Skills4EOSC Competence Centre Charter. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10048176
R2	https://www.skills4eosc.eu/network
R3	https://www.icdi.it/en/
R4	https://grnet.gr/
R5	https://csc.fi/en/our-expertise/research-data-management/
R6	https://snd.se/en
R7	https://osc.ukim.mk/
R8	https://recherche.data.gouv.fr/en
R9	https://www.lnds.lu/
R10	https://pg.edu.pl/en/openscience
R11	https://www.rdm.kit.edu/english/index.php
R12	https://cnudst.rnrt.tn/en
R13	https://zenodo.org/records/15111345
R14	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=SArus1oeOEE
R15	https://www.skills4eosc.eu/participate/events/workshop-making-the-competence-centres-network-sustainable-and-enhanced
R16	https://www.skills4eosc.eu/participate/events/building-a-sustainable-future-for-open-science-skills4eosc-competence-centres-workshop
R17	https://www.skills4eosc.eu/participate/events/building-capacity-for-open-science
R18	https://www.skills4eosc.eu/network/competence-centres/setting-up-a-cc/ccs-practical-guide

R19	https://www.skills4eosc.eu/network/competence-centres/setting-up-a-cc
R20	Candela, L., Green, D., Lembinen, L., Linés, C., Vudragovic, D., Zimniewicz, M., Prandoni, C., Di Giorgio, S., & Corleto, A. (2024). D7.2 Sample of services toolset: a practical guideline (1.0). Skills4EOSC Project Deliverable. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14230226
R21	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1PcdFEuYunHbIZQNeOz7jN5y7UqzhEJqp/view
R22	https://drive.google.com/drive/u/0/folders/1DVxvPQqBAdxeIEvN051oAUuB76Uw8CsE
R23	https://chat.eudat.eu/skills4eosc/channels/town-square
R24	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1v4OjQdo_42d0uqjOtfcuev7_2Y1UEAtm/view
R25	https://indico.kit.edu/event/4547/
R26	https://indico.kit.edu/event/4295/
R27	https://indico.kit.edu/event/4711/
R28	https://indico.kit.edu/event/4871/
R29	https://indico.kit.edu/event/4943/
R30	https://www.skills4eosc.eu/network/user-support-network
R31	https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/Skills4EOSC-UserSupportNetwork-ApplicationForm
R32	https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/